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EXPLICIT VS. IMPLICIT VOCABULARY LEARNING IN ESP CLASSES: INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY TO ENHANCE LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract

Vocabulary is crucial to the teaching and learning of the English language in general and even more important in ESP classes. Like many other specialized fields of study and professional settings, English for Specific Purposes, likewise English for sports and physical activity, demands the development of fundamental language skills, which are mainly promoted by understanding the field's semi-technical and technical lexicon in addition to grammar proficiency. Students will advance academically and professionally as a result of their understanding and proficiency of sports and physical education terminology. Furthermore, English is the common language in practically every academic, professional, and research setting. This is also true in the world of sports, as well as in sporting events and competitions.

The purpose of this study was to ascertain whether the materials and activities designed were contributive to student learning, specifically examining whether the textbook, additional audio/visual resources, and written materials were beneficial for students in terms of acquiring vocabulary. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, this study aims to provide insights into how these learning strategies, augmented by technology, contribute to the vocabulary acquisition process in ESP learners.

Keywords: English for Specific Purposes, language acquisition, vocabulary learning, implicit learning, explicit learning, technology use

Introduction

Vocabulary acquisition is a cornerstone of language learning, and its significance is particularly pronounced in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classes, where learners are tasked with mastering domain-specific language for professional or academic contexts. In ESP, the strategies employed for vocabulary learning can vary widely, with two prominent approaches being explicit and implicit learning. Explicit vocabulary learning typically involves direct instruction, such as memorization, word lists, and deliberate practice, while implicit learning occurs more naturally through exposure to context and language use in real-world scenarios. As the role of technology in education continues to grow, it presents a unique opportunity to bridge these two approaches, potentially enhancing both explicit and implicit vocabulary acquisition. Technological tools such as language learning apps, online exercises, and immersive environments have revolutionized the way vocabulary is introduced, reinforced, and practiced in the classroom. This research aims to explore the interplay between explicit and implicit vocabulary learning strategies in ESP classes, with a focus on how technology can be integrated to optimize language learning outcomes. By examining the strengths and challenges of each learning approach in conjunction with technological innovations, this study seeks to provide valuable insights for educators aiming to enhance ESP students' vocabulary proficiency.

The importance of grammar has been studied and

recognized in numerous ELT methodologies; on the other hand, vocabulary has not been the focus of many studies or scholars. According to Decarrico (2001: 285), "vocabulary has not always been recognized as a priority in language teaching." Words are the basis of language, and thus the basis of communication. Without words, it is possible to know everything about the grammatical structure of a language, but yet to be unable to make a single utterance. (Bowen & Marks 2002: 106)

The indispensable part that vocabulary plays in language teaching and learning has led scholars and researchers to consider it more closely, nowadays, thus giving this aspect of language learning the importance it deserves. The importance of vocabulary and its significance in learning a language has become more accepted nowadays. Vocabulary is a basic component of language proficiency which provides the basis for learners' performance in other skills, such as speaking, reading, listening and writing. Griffiths (2003, 2006) highlights the central role that vocabulary occupies in language proficiency, advocating for integrated instructional approaches, and emphasizing the empowerment of learners to take charge of their vocabulary development.

Vocabulary occupies a central role in foreign and/or second language teaching and learning (FL & SL) and it is one of the defining feature of English for specific purposes (ESP) as agreed and confirmed by many researchers in this field. As stated by Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998: 5) ESP may be related to or

designed for specific disciplines, necessitating the teaching of specialized vocabulary pertinent to those fields. According to Robinson (1991: 4) "... a characteristic, or even a critical feature, of ESP is that a course should involve specialist language and content."

Students' progress and acquisition are affected by both teaching approaches and learning strategies. In order to succeed in vocabulary teaching, the teacher should engage his/her students emotionally first and discuss or negotiate the meaning of newly encountered words with each other and later with the teacher. In this way, the students will store the words in their memory and retrieve them in similar situations and contexts, as stated by some others emotional involvement helps to learn.

As well as facilitating vocabulary acquisition, student involvement fosters learning autonomy and holds individuals accountable for their own education. The teacher should monitor students' autonomous learning in the context of ESP vocabulary learning in order to teach them vocabulary items that require extra attention, aspects that need to be revised, or even to provide them with the tools they need to acquire these words and transform them into professional active vocabulary.

Essential components of vocabulary teaching and acquisition

There are many categories that can be taught to know the word properly; nevertheless, it is not necessary for learners to know all of them about all the words they have learnt.

According to Harmer (1991: 158) to know the word involves knowing its:

Meaning (its definition) - meanings in context, sense relations (synonyms, antonyms)

Usage – collocations, idioms and metaphors, style and register

Form – spelling and pronunciation, prefixes and suffixes, parts of speech

Grammar – irregular forms, phrasal verbs, adverbs and adjectives.

To teach students these aspects of the word, depending on the stage of the students as well as their level and learning style, teachers commonly use some techniques, often referred to as the traditional ones, as listed and explained below.

General English vocabulary includes grammatical words, basic lexical words, and auxiliaries, while "special lexical items appear in most professions, and every field has special vocabulary to cover abstract concepts" (Hatch and Brown 1995, p. 312). The authors Kennedy and Bolitho (1984: 56-58) provide the following specialized word categories for teaching purposes:

- Technical Abbreviations – e.g. km/h, km, m3.

- Symbols and Formulae – they are the subject matter of the learner's speciality, and the teacher may explain their function in the text.

- Sub-technical vocabulary refers to "words or vocabulary items that possess one or more standard English definitions but acquire extended meanings (technical or specialized) in specific contexts (Trimble 1985: 129). Alternatively, as defined by Kennedy and

Bolitho, these are words that are not exclusive to a particular subject area but frequently appear in scientific and technical literature (1984: 57-58). It is essential for the ESP teacher to clarify the specialized meanings that these terms hold within the particular technical text.

- Highly technical vocabulary – these terms are very specific and so may be less comprehensible. Every subject has its set of highly technical vocabulary and Kennedy & Bolitho (1984: 57) suggest that these terms "should arise, in context, in the specialist classes and are not normally the teacher's responsibility".

There are three basic approaches to teaching and learning vocabulary that lead to the successful development of the learner's lexicon (Coady, 1997a; Hulstijn, Hollander, & Greidanus, 1996). The three methods are incidental learning, explicit instruction, and independent strategy development. While Decarrico (2001) distinguishes between **explicit learning**, where vocabulary is directly taught through deliberate instruction, and **implicit learning**, where vocabulary is acquired incidentally through exposure and context. The author (Decarrico 2001) argues that both methods play essential roles in language development, with explicit instruction helping learners notice and retain unfamiliar words, while implicit learning fosters deeper, more natural language use. Incidental learning (i.e., acquiring vocabulary as a secondary result of activities like reading and listening) necessitates that educators create opportunities for extensive engagement in reading and listening. Explicit instruction entails identifying the vocabulary that learners need, introducing new words, expanding word knowledge, and fostering fluency with familiar words. Independent strategy development includes practicing context clues for guessing meanings and teaching learners how to use dictionaries (Hunt & Beglar 1998).

Teachers usually employ one of these traditional approaches to present new vocabulary to their students; visual techniques, verbal techniques and translation.

1. visual techniques - teachers try to establish a link between the word and meaning by using one of the following means or techniques depending on the word to be taught such as realia, i.e. objects in the class, pictures, photos, drawings, flashcards, slides, wallcharts as well as miming, gestures, actions, facial expressions

The techniques abovementioned are used with concrete words so that they are presented easily, concretely as well as directly and in an interesting way.

Depending on the words to be taught and their meaning or being concrete or abstract, other ways to present them may be used.

2. verbal techniques- These techniques apply to abstract vocabulary items.

a-by giving examples of the type, e.g. to illustrate the meaning of super-ordinates

b-by giving illustrative situations, to explain abstract words, for instance

c-through definition

d-with synonyms/antonyms

e-by using scales for gradable items

3. Translation, used sensibly, can be a useful

technique to convey meaning as:

-it saves time

-it allows checking correct comprehension, when necessary in the case of false friends

These techniques constitute direct or explicit vocabulary teaching. Due to time and condition constraints, it is impossible to teach your students all the vocabulary directly or explicitly/intentionally. Thus, for this reason, the teacher should equip the students with strategies so that they can continue learning new vocabulary outside the ESP classroom as well as after the course.

ESP alike FL, SL is acquired through micro and macro mental processes: the first engages attention; memory; integration; restructuring and monitoring through which learners modify the interlanguage systems and improve their second language output consciously and intentionally; the second includes the distinction between intentional learning and incidental learning; and also the distinction between explicit and implicit learning.

Learning vocabulary incidentally means memorizing words and expressions through communicative activities mainly through receptive ones, i.e. reading and listening, while trying to learn something else. The learner's attention is focused on the meaning in context rather than on the form of language (Hulstijn 2008). So incidental learning is closely connected with the context and clues to meaning, as to particular new or field-specific words, derive from familiarization with a certain situation which includes the topic, the setting, the speakers or communicator, the purpose as well as other elements of textuality and intertextuality. Context is the main element which helps incidental vocabulary learning. Guessing words from context is seen as the opposition to 'direct intentional learning and teaching of vocabulary' (Nation, 2003).

According to Nation (2003), "indirect vocabulary learning should take up significantly more time in a language course compared to direct vocabulary learning tasks." Since it is difficult to teach all course vocabulary explicitly, it becomes one of the teacher's responsibilities to motivate students to create their own vocabulary learning strategies for continued vocabulary acquisition beyond the course. Gairns & Redman (1993:76.) note that "this not only makes the learner take more accountability for their own learning but also allows for a greater focus on individual needs." This implies that activities focused on language in context (contextualization) should be prioritized over those aimed at the de-contextualization of new vocabulary words.

Understanding the various approaches to teaching vocabulary—both incidental and intentional—can have a significant impact on how effectively vocabulary is taught to learners. According to Hedge (2000), these strategies can be classified as either cognitive, which involves direct mental processes to comprehend and

retain new words, or meta-cognitive, which encompasses indirect methods that support the conscious effort to memorize new vocabulary. Decarrico highlights the need for balanced instruction that integrates form, meaning, and usage, allowing learners to develop a functional and flexible vocabulary base (Decarrico 2001)

Research methodology

This study focuses on the ways that students prefer and use to learn new specific vocabulary in their field of study, i.e. sports and physical activity, and also on the effective ways regarding their progress in vocabulary acquisition. In other words, based on a questionnaire and analyses of the results of their language tests on specific vocabulary the paper will identify which way they prefer to learn new words.

The subjects of this study were 70 students in their first year during the academic years 2023-24 and 2024-25. The questionnaire was drafted based on the types of activities held at ESP classes and students were explained that it was for research purposes which findings would also be reflected on the tasks and content of the remaining classes. They were sent an online questionnaire that aimed to identify which types of classroom activities were most helpful to them to acquire a new specific vocabulary of their field of study, as well as it asked students to state which of the activities used in the classroom they found more challenging.

The reliability of the survey instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The overall alpha coefficient was 0.87, indicating an acceptable level of internal consistency among the survey items

Research findings and discussions

The survey results indicate that while a significant number of students find Sports English and its vocabulary challenging (60% and 62.9% respectively), the majority recognize the value of vocabulary exercises (68.6%) in supporting their learning. Interactive tasks such as word games (85.7%), matching definitions (82.9%), and gap-filling activities (80%) were identified as the most effective methods for vocabulary acquisition, whereas guessing from context was less favored. Most students (71.4%) felt that definitions alone were insufficient, highlighting the importance of additional materials, with 88.6% affirming the helpfulness of extra reading. Notably, 97.1% reported that vocabulary exercises contributed to their ability to use new terms in academic tasks such as presentations and assignments. Consolidation was best supported through game commentaries (94.3%) and problem-solving activities (74.3%). However, only 17.1% of students adopted new strategies for vocabulary learning, and 25.7% encountered difficulties with the new vocabulary type. Encouragingly, all respondents (100%) believe the vocabulary being learned is relevant to their academic and professional development (see Table 1 below).

Table 1

Questionnaire statistics			
Statistics of responses Questions	Percent yes	Percent no	Valid/ Total
1. Is learning Sports English challenging for you?	60.0	40.0	70/ 70
2. Do you consider Sports-related vocabulary hard to learn?	62.9	37.1	70/ 70
3. Do you think vocabulary exercises are helpful in improving your vocabulary?	68.6	31.4	70/ 70
Which types of activities support your learning of new words?			
Multiple-choice questions	68.6	31.4	35/ 35
Matching words to their definitions	82.9	17.1	70/ 70
Using online dictionaries	37.1	62.9	70/ 70
Guessing meaning from context	68.6	31.4	70/ 70
Playing word games	85.7	14.3	70/ 70
Completing gap-fill exercises	80.0	20.0	70/ 70
Solving crosswords	54.3	45.7	70/ 70
Other (e.g., sentence building, using new words in dialogues or conversations)	65.7	34.3	70/ 70
5. Do definitions of new terminology help you memorize them?	28.6	71.4	70/ 70
6. Do the extra reading materials help you learn the new words successfully?	88.6	11.4	70/ 70
7. Do vocabulary tasks help you with productive use of new terminology?	97.1	2.9	70/ 70
8. Which tasks help you consolidate field-specific vocabulary?			
• game and event commentaries	94.3	5.7	70/ 70
• problem solutions	74.3	25.7	70/ 70
9. Did you start using any new techniques and strategies for learning and remembering new words?	17.1	82.9	70/ 70
10. Did any problems or difficulties occur when you started to deal with the new type of vocabulary?	25.7	34.3	70/ 70
		40.0	70/ 70
11. Do you find the terminology useful for academic/professional performance?	100.0	0	70/ 70

Most students have chosen the more difficult types of exercises, the answers provided by them to the question about the activities mentioned in question 4 and they had to choose at least two, they answered: crosswords and sentence building, or using new words in their own written or spoken texts, as well as working with on-line dictionaries or multiple choice exercises. The qualitative analysis of this question helps to distinguish the types of tasks the students find difficult to complete and explains the students' attitude to certain types of activities outlined in the previous question.

Moreover, besides the survey presented in Table 1, in open discussion students state the reasons they are having difficulties with sports vocabulary are: their General English proficiency which affects learning the new items they deal with in the ESP classroom. About 43% of the students stated that they are having difficulties learning new field-specific vocabulary because of their low level of general English knowledge. They also say that they have not started using any new strategies in order to learn new vocabulary. The majority of students with a low level of general English knowledge find it difficult to use new items of vocabulary in their own sentences and texts and they also think that crosswords are challenging for them. On the other hand, these students think that gap-filling activities, word games and crosswords are helpful to learn new vocabulary. Moreover, despite these difficulties, they find new

vocabulary not very difficult as 14 of them answered questions 1 and 2 'a little', and 2 of them answered 'no'.

The majority of the students (88.6%) stated that extra materials, video/audio and written ones, help in their learning of sports and PE vocabulary and stressed that vocabulary practice exercises (97.1%) helped them consolidate new vocabulary items.

When answering if they had started using new strategies to help them learn and consolidate sports-specific vocabulary, 5 of them said that they had started reading authentic materials, such as news, books and surfing on the net in order to help them enrich their vocabulary. Some others have started watching matches and sports events with commentaries in English.

Students have commented that sports vocabulary is valuable and they appreciate the fact that they are attaining a lot of vocabulary items related to their field of study. The majority of the students, 26 of them confess that they are not facing any problems in the ESP class, respectively with activities to learn field-specific vocabulary; 22 of them are facing difficulties because the vocabulary they are dealing with is unfamiliar to them and it is the first time they are encountering them; 16 of them say that the problems are due to their general English competence, i.e. their English level is elementary; 4 of the subjects have not responded to the question and 1 of the students states that he/she is facing problems because of the different

teaching approach as well as for the specificity of the terminology dealt in the classroom. A general opinion stated by them is also that they are dealing with a large amount of new sports vocabulary which makes it more challenging for them to learn and master.

Conclusions

The results of the questionnaire confirmed that the best way to teach vocabulary efficiently and to make students confident in using newly learned field-specific vocabulary is through various activities to present, practice and consolidate new lexicon. The students also have to distinguish between general, semi-technical and technical vocabulary of their field and profession in order to make the learning process easier, or the noticing stage that is important. The teacher should carefully select the vocabulary to be taught during the course and emphasize specialized vocabulary to ensure correct understanding and usage of the respective terminology. Another objective aimed by teachers should be enabling students to make use of vocabulary learning strategies that will last and be employed beyond the classroom and university settings. It is also important to present authentic materials to the students to help them know how the learned vocabulary is used. Moreover, authentic materials, as well as extensive reading and listening, should be used in order to provide the basis of incidental vocabulary learning, as some of the students find it useful and have already started reading materials and watching events to know more about sports, regulations and beside them to build on their sports vocabulary.

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